

Report on text anonymisation tools

Deliverable ID	D17.1- Report on text anonymisation tools
Work Package Reference	WP17
Issue	1.0
Due Date of Deliverable	30/06/2025
Submission Date	30/06/2025
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Lead Partner	ULE
Contributors	ULE
Grant Agreement No	101131957
Call ID	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01
Digital Object Identifier (DOI):	10.5281/zenodo.15533161
Website:	https://eosc-siesta.eu/

**Funded by
the European Union**

¹ **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Author	CRedit statement ⁽¹⁾
Eniafe Festus Ayetiran (ULE)	Writing – original draft
Víctor González Castro (ULE)	Writing – original draft
Laura Fernández Robles (ULE)	Writing – original draft
Eduardo Fidalgo Fernández (ULE)	Writing – review & editing
Enrique Alegre Gutiérrez (ULE)	Writing – review & editing
Rocío Alaiz Rodríguez (ULE)	Writing – review & editing

¹ CRedit (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) specifies author contribution. Choose between: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Issue	Date	Description	Author(s)
0.1	10/04/2025	Table of contents	Víctor González Castro
0.2	30/05/2025	First full draft	Eniafe Festus Ayetiran, Laura Fernández Robles, Víctor González Castro
1.0	25/06/2025	Final version (approved by PMB)	Eniafe Festus Ayetiran, Laura Fernández Robles, Víctor González Castro

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	4
1.1. Motivation and significance of the pilot case	5
1.2. Review of the state-of-the-art	6
2. SIESTA personas	8
3. Work package organisation and task structure	9
4. Data life cycle point of view	10
4.1. Data collection and data sources	11
4.2. Data processing	11
4.3. Data storage.....	12
4.4. Data access.....	13
4.5. Data exploitation.....	13
4.6. Data sharing and dissemination.....	13
4.7. Data disposal	14
5. Assessment of models for text anonymisation	14
5.1. Evaluation dataset: CECILIA.....	14
5.2. Assessed models	15
6. Results of text anonymisation experiments	16
7. Summary, Conclusion and future work	18
7.1. Summary of key findings and contributions.....	18
7.2. Future work and suggestions for improvement	18
7.3. Limitations and challenges	19
References	20
Appendices	23
Appendix A - Text generation engine.....	23
Appendix B - CECILIA entities	24
Appendix C - Differences and equivalences among CECILIA, CoNLL-03 and OntoNotes	26
Appendix D - Comparison of CECILIA with other annotation schemes	30

1. INTRODUCTION

This section presents the background information on the current status of text anonymisation. It also discusses and clarifies descriptions of terms in text anonymisation, which are often used interchangeably within the field.

It is becoming increasingly necessary to share various forms of textual data among agencies, organisations, governments, and other entities. It is of great importance to protect the private information in this data. Publishing individual private information (often referred to as personally identifiable information (PII) in the field of data privacy) may have serious effects on the individuals. Privacy regulations will never be 100% effective due to breaches and other unforeseen events, such as accidental release or compromised data infrastructure. The development of data technologies aimed at preserving privacy is essential to ensure compliance with regulations, especially since manual privacy protection on data is an almost impossible task due to the ever-growing amount of data containing personal identifiable information.

In the context of work package (WP) 17, when an Online Service Provider (or its users) identifies a potential cyber-incident on their networks, they refer the case to relevant authorities, such as national or international cybersecurity agencies. Such referrals often contain information about the suspected source, including email addresses, IP addresses, and other data. These authorities review the reported data and, if it matches known patterns of cyber incidents based on their databases, they take appropriate actions, even notifying Law Enforcement Agencies (LEA) with enhanced information, such as the geo-localization of the reported case.

Currently, there is no standardised tool that Authorities and LEAs can use for anonymizing cyber incident reports or similar data. As real data cannot be provided to researchers, training machine learning models to automatically classify such content presents significant challenges. There are presently two solutions: (i) to anonymize data manually, which is very time-consuming and out of the scope of LEAs or, (ii) to use other generic text anonymisation tools, which are not used because they are not specifically oriented to this task, may miss critical information or the data generated by existing tools produce text that cannot be used to train machine learning models.

Like most areas of research, the terms used in unstructured text anonymisation are often defined differently by different scholars and are used interchangeably within the field. However, the term “anonymisation” is generally used to cover the entire field that deals with the complete removal or replacement of personal information in sensitive data. For the sake of clarity and consistency, we define the following terms, the majority of which are used within this report. All references to person or personal might be extended to other entities whose data is recorded, such as organizations or computers, if their identity must remain confidential:

- ‘Confidential Attribute’ or ‘Confidential Information’: Personal information which should remain private except with the informed consent of the owner.
- ‘Record’: A collection of attributes belonging to a person, e.g., id, name, etc., each of which can be used to identify the person directly.

- ‘Direct Identifier’: An attribute in a record belonging to a person that can be directly used to identify an individual, typically with one of them serving as a unique identifier.
- ‘Quasi Identifier’: A personal attribute in a record, which cannot be directly used to identify a person, but can be combined with other data to reveal a person’s identity.
- ‘De-identification’: It involves the complete removal of direct identifiers from data to prevent the identification of individuals.
- ‘Anonymisation’: It deals with the removal of both direct and quasi identifiers from data. The goal is to prevent attackers from having a clue about individuals. This is because even with quasi-identifiers, attackers may be able to trace the subject. However, this term is used to generally refer to the field that deals with the removal or replacement of personal information from text.
- ‘Pseudonymization’: A process that replaces direct identifiers with pseudonyms, allowing data to be processed in a less identifiable form while retaining the possibility of re-identification under specific, controlled circumstances².
- ‘Personally Identifiable Information’ (PII): PII encompasses both direct and quasi identifiers through which a subject may be identified directly or indirectly, respectively.

1.1. MOTIVATION AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PILOT CASE

This pilot case is focused on the anonymisation of unstructured texts, specifically cyber incident reports that Cybersecurity Emergency Response Teams (CERTs) elaborate on their daily activities. CERTs usually need to categorise these reports depending on certain cyber incident taxonomies. Due to the volume of incidents they receive, it would help them to automate this task using Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine/Deep Learning-based methods (Delgado et al., 2024, Staab et al. 2025, Xiaodan et al., 2024, Hassan et al., 2023). However, since these reports contain sensitive information from individuals or organisations, CERTs cannot disclose them, making the development of NLP-based classification models challenging due to the lack of real data to train them. Therefore, a tool to automatically anonymise these reports would be very useful, allowing them to be shared securely with researchers for this purpose. The anonymisation should remove all sensitive personal information, while preserving the information that makes it possible to train NLP models to classify cyber incidents accurately. A tool like this would enhance the EOSC capabilities to share data securely, according to the FAIR principles.

Research on the anonymisation of structured data has gained wider interest and a higher level of sophistication than that of the less mature field of unstructured data, which is still in its formative stages. Due to the infancy level of research on unstructured data,

² <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/anonymisation/pseudonymisation/>

there is a notable lack of high-quality open-access datasets available for conducting cutting-edge studies.

The confidentiality requirements of the data contained in the cyber incident reports issued by the corresponding authorities, combined with their limited accessibility, made us aware of the need to build a synthetic reports dataset, with information analogous to that which might be present in real cyber incident reports. Moreover, we conducted extensive experiments using various text anonymisation models to evaluate their capabilities. The experiments comprise state-of-the-art models as outlined in section 5.2.

The use case objectives are:

- To assess state-of-the-art methods to process and anonymise unstructured texts, with the goal of detecting the entities susceptible to be anonymised, e.g. IP addresses, names, places, etc.
- To build a synthetic dataset of sensitive textual data. Due to the scarcity of publicly available real cyber incident reports, we will create a synthetic dataset that simulates real reports.

The tools assessed in this pilot case could be applied to other domains in which unstructured text data is used.

1.2. REVIEW OF THE STATE-OF-THE-ART

In this section, we describe the current state of progress in unstructured text anonymisation. Unlike structured data, where anonymisation techniques are more mature and efficient, unstructured data presents greater challenges. To ensure a comprehensive overview, we adopted a systematic review approach to guide both the selection and reporting of relevant works, focusing on studies published from 2020 onwards.

According to Lison et al. (2021), text anonymisation methods can be broadly grouped into two main approaches. On the one hand are the approaches based on natural language processing, which are often framed as sequence labelling tasks, mainly named entity recognition (NER). Beyond NER, other NLP-based methods also employ strategies to obfuscate sensitive information. In general, NLP-based methods treat personal identifiers as entities to be detected. Most of the existing research in this area has focused on the medical domain, where standardised guidelines are provided for de-identification. Methods in this approach can be: (i) rule-based, which use regular expression patterns, dictionaries and heuristics to detect and redact PII; (ii) machine learning-based, which trains NER models to identify PII; or (iii) hybrid methods that combine both. State-of-the-art neural architectures, including recurrent neural networks with character embeddings and bidirectional transformers, have further enhanced performance in this domain.

On the other hand are the techniques based on privacy-preserving data publishing (PPDP). Unlike NLP approaches, PPDP methods explicitly model disclosure risk and apply privacy constraints to anonymise documents. These methods can protect direct identifiers (e.g., names, passport numbers) as well as quasi-identifiers (e.g., age, profession, postal code) that, when combined, could lead to re-identification. The

effectiveness of PPDP depends on assumptions about an adversary’s background knowledge. PPDP techniques typically frame anonymisation as an optimisation problem, seeking the minimal set of masking operations, such as suppression or generalisation, needed to satisfy a given privacy model. While PPDP approaches offer stronger formal privacy guarantees compared to sequence labelling methods, they also face limitations, including scalability challenges. In particular, PPDP methods often reduce documents to collections of terms, disregarding the contextual relationships between them. Hence, they are not as robust for unstructured texts as NLP-based methods. Methods in this approach mainly enforce differential privacy bounds.

While most NLP-based methods focus mainly on direct identifiers, which are usually named entities, PPDP-based methods prioritise privacy first and thereby tend to cater for both direct and quasi identifiers by enforcing certain privacy conditions based on disclosure risk. We juxtapose these methods in Table 1, identifying the approach, the specific algorithm(s) and the dataset utilised. The evaluation metrics cover two primary evaluation criteria for text anonymisation, namely the utility and privacy preservation of the resulting anonymised text.

S/N	Work	Approach	Year	Algorithm(s)	Evaluation Metrics	Dataset(s)
1	Text anonymisation benchmark (TAB) (Pilán et al. 2022)	NLP and PPDP	2022	Neural NER based on RoBERTa, commercial tool (Presidio)	Recall, Precision, entity-level recall on direct identifier (ER_d), entity-level recall on quasi identifier (ER_q) and weighted token precision (WP_{d+q})	TAB
2	Language models are advanced anonymisers (Staab et al. 2025)	NLP	2025	Large language models (LLMs), including GPT4 among others, commercial products such as Azure, Presidio etc.	Accuracy	PersonalReddit, and Synthetic Reddit comments
3	Robust utility-preserving text anonymisation based on LLMs (Xiaodan et al., 2024)	NLP	2024	Multi-objective optimization with LLMs	Success rate, confidence scores, precision, recall, F1, accuracy and loss	DB-bio and PersonalReddit
4	Enhancing text anonymisation via re-identification risk-based explainability (Manzanares-Salor and Sánchez 2025)	NLP and PPDP	2025	Multiple NER-based algorithms combined with K-anonymity using neural LMs	Precision, recall, F1, F2, normalized mutual information (NMI)	TAB
5	Violating privacy via inference with LLMs (Staab et al. 2024)	NLP	2024	Large language models (LLMs)	Accuracy	PersonalReddit
6	Resource-efficient anonymisation of textual data via knowledge distillation from LLMs (Deußler et al. 2025)	NLP	2025	LLMs via knowledge distillation	Recall and F1	Text from various sources
7	Customization scenarios for de-identification of clinical notes (Hartman et al. 2020)	NLP	2020	NER via pretrained token embedding and bidirectional recurrent neural network	Precision, recall and F1	i2b2-2014, i2b2-2006, physionet, mimic3- radiology, mimic3- echo, mimic3- discharge
8	InstaHide: Instance-hiding Schemes for Private Distributed Learning (Huang et al. 2020)	NLP	2020	Encryption via mixup method with experiments on inside-dataset and cross-dataset InstaHide schemes	Precision, recall and F1	MNIST, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100 and ImageNe
9	TextHide: Tackling Data Privacy in Language Understanding Tasks (Huang et al. 2020)	NLP	2020	Incorporation of encryption into a framework for fine-tuning Language models (LMs)	Accuracy, F1, Pearson, Spearman and Matthew’s correlations,	General Language Understanding Evaluation (GLUE) benchmark
10	A privacy-preserving approach to extraction of personal information (Hathurusinghe et al., 2021)	NLP	2020	Federated learning through BERT-based NER	Precision, recall and F1	WikiPii
11	anonymisation for the GDPR in the context of citizen and customer relationship management and NLP	NLP	2020	Substitution (Pseudonymization) achieved through existing NER tools	Precision, recall and F1	No specified name, proprietary
12	Privacy and utility-preserving NLP with anonymised Data (Yermilov et al., 2023)	NLP	2023	Pseudonymization achieved through NER, sequence-to-sequence modeling and LLM	False negatives, Precision, recall and F1, ROUGE 1, 2 and L	CoNLL-2003, CNN/DM, and IMDB

S/N	Work	Approach	Year	Algorithm(s)	Evaluation Metrics	Dataset(s)
13	Bootstrapping text anonymisation models with distant supervision (Papadopoulou et al. 2022)	NLP and PPDP	2022	Language model (LM) fine-tuning with distant supervision achieved through knowledge graph	Precision, recall, entity-level recall on direct identifier (ER_d), entity-level recall on quasi identifier (ER_q) and weighted token precision (WP_{d+q})	No specified name; wikipedia-based
14	Utility-preserving privacy protection (Hassan et al., 2023)	NLP and PPDP	2023	Similarity-based on word embeddings	Precision, recall F1, suppression, generalization and average masked terms	Wikipedia articles on movie actors
15	De-identification of free-text medical records (Johnson et al., 2020)	NLP	2020	Bidirectional transformers	Precision, recall and F1	i2b2-2014, i2b2-2006, PhysioNet, Dernoncourt2014 and Lee
16	De-Identifying Student PII (Singhal et al. 2024)	NLP	2024	LLM precisely GPT-4	Precision, recall and Cohen's Kappa	Posts from Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)
17	De-identification of privacy-related entities in job postings (Jensen et al., 2021)	NLP	2021	Long short-term memory (LSTM) networks and BERT (Devlin et al. 2019)	Precision, recall and F1	JOBSTACK Dataset

Table 1: State-of-the-art text anonymisation methods

2. SIESTA PERSONAS

For our use case, we identified 3 major stakeholders, otherwise referred to as personas, which include the data rights' holder, the SIESTA platform operator and the data user, defined as follows:

1. The **data rights holder** is the entity (individual or organisation) legally and ethically responsible for collections of cybersecurity incident reports, such as a cybersecurity technician responsible for managing incident reports in a Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT). This persona oversees the governance of datasets that may contain personally identifiable or sensitive information, and authorises their use within the SIESTA platform. The data rights holder decides on access privilege, the licence for use, and the technical details required to use the data. These details include the metadata, format, and structure of the data. The data from the data rights holder cannot be released in its original form because of the presence of sensitive information. Anonymising the text will make it possible to share it with other people, who can create classification models to automate text classification.
2. The **data user** is the entity (individual or organisation), such as a researcher, analyst, or data scientist, engaged in the study of cybersecurity incidents using anonymised textual data. This persona interacts with datasets within the SIESTA platform to train classification models, extract patterns, or answer specific research questions, among other purposes, without ever accessing raw sensitive data.
Data scientists who work in a CERT, and want to use the cyber incidents report data to develop machine and deep learning models, can directly access the original cyber incidents. Data scientists working outside a CERT can access the anonymised cyber incident reports through the SIESTA platform under the licence stipulated by the data rights holder.

3. The **SIESTA platform operator** is the person or organisation responsible for the management of the entire SIESTA platform (e.g. cloud, server, etc). In other words, the SIESTA platform operator manages the entire data hosting infrastructure and provides services to both the data rights holder and the data user, ensuring data is made available and accessible.

3. WORK PACKAGE ORGANISATION AND TASK STRUCTURE

We organise the work package comprising two main tasks:

- Task 17.1: Building of a synthetic dataset of sensitive textual data
- Task 17.2: Entity detection in unstructured texts

We organised these two tasks into several activities, along with the preparation of this report, spanning 15 months as presented below. A Gantt chart of the presented activities is shown in Figure 1.

1. Task 17.1 Activity 1 (Literature survey on synthetic data): Review of the literature on synthetic dataset generation and dataset structure for unstructured text anonymisation. The insights gained enabled the team to make informed decisions about the appropriate tools and models for generating the dataset. The activity was conducted between months 3 and 5 of the project timeline.
2. Task 17.1 Activity 2 (Seed sample generation and script development): This activity involves generating seed samples for the creation of the synthetic dataset, as well as developing a script used to produce the synthetic texts. It was carried out between months 6 and 8 of the project timeline.
3. Task 17.1 Activity 3 (Script implementation and debugging): This activity involved implementing the previously developed script and conducting debugging based on the quality and generation speed of the synthetic texts produced. It was carried out between months 9 and 11 of the project timeline.
4. Task 17.1 Activity 4 (Finalisation of dataset generation and documentation): The dataset generation is finalised in this, and an internal report on the task is written.. This activity was conducted between months 12 and 14 of the project timeline.
5. Task 17.1 Activity 5 (Data storage, sharing and dissemination): It was carried out between months 15 and 16 of the project timeline. The data can be found at this [link](https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/WP17/tree/main/Task%2017.1)³.
6. Task 17.2 Activity 1 (Literature survey on unstructured text anonymisation state-of-the-art): In this activity, we survey the state-of-the-art on text anonymisation models, the existing datasets, evaluation metrics, current challenges and

³ <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/WP17/tree/main/Task%2017.1>

research opportunities. It was conducted between months 3 and 5 of the project timeline.

7. Task 17.2 Activity 2 (Experimentation with text anonymisation models): This activity involves experimentation with several text anonymisation models. The timeline is between the 6th and 12th months of the work package commencement.
8. Task 17.2 Activity 3 (Models evaluation): This activity focused on experimenting with a range of text anonymisation models to assess their performance and suitability for the use case. It was carried out between months 6 and 12 of the work package timeline.
9. Task 17.2 Activity 4 (Draft report on text anonymisation): This activity involved preparing the draft report documenting the experiments and evaluation results related to text anonymisation. It was conducted between months 15 and 16 of the project timeline.
10. Integrated report writing, review and editing: During months 17 and 18, we integrated the reports from the two tasks. Review and editing was also carried out.

		Year 1										Year 2					
Month		3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Task 17.1	Activity 1	█	█	█													
	Activity 2				█	█	█										
	Activity 3							█	█	█							
	Activity 4										█	█	█				
	Activity 5													█	█		
Task 17.2	Activity 1	█	█	█													
	Activity 2				█	█	█	█	█	█	█						
	Activity 3											█	█				
	Activity 4													█	█		
Integrated report															█	█	

Figure 1: Work package organisation and structure

4. DATA LIFE CYCLE POINT OF VIEW

In the context of Task 17.1, we created a synthetic dataset simulating cyber incident reports issued by the corresponding authorities that typically contain personally identifiable information. Thus, it does not suppose any disclosure of critical information.

SIESTA will develop a tool that enables the training of machine learning models on anonymised text data. The synthetic dataset can be used as a benchmark to evaluate the performance of the models created with this tool on both its original and anonymised versions. Therefore, it allows the training of machine learning models and the comparison of the performance of the different models in the classification of the cyber incident category.

This dataset is currently ready for performing non-supervised classification tasks. It will be enhanced so that it can be used for supervised tasks by annotating (a) the personal data is localised and categorised into types, and (b) each cyber incident has a label indicating its type. Cyber incidents in the dataset will be annotated according to a

modified version, as described below, of the cyber incident taxonomy proposed by the Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE)⁴. We have not been able to carry out the annotations yet, due to some unexpected events, detailed in Section 7.3, that have delayed the completion of the WP tasks. Nonetheless, the current lack of annotations do not interfere with the rest of the Work Packages, either ongoing or future work packages.

The development, management and dissemination of the dataset follow the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability. The details of the text generation engine are presented in Appendix A.

4.1. DATA COLLECTION AND DATA SOURCES

We created the synthetic dataset using real publicly available cyber incidents descriptions as a foundation. Since these public sources typically contain limited personal information compared to official CERT reports, we enriched the generated reports with fictitious personal data. Additionally, we incorporated insights and structure derived from a small number of real CERT cyber incidents reports to which the ULE research group has access.

Based on INCIBE's taxonomy, we identified 10 classes of cyber incidents and several subclasses within them. We modified this taxonomy to incorporate elements from other popular cyber incident taxonomies, such as the ENISA Cyber Incident Taxonomy⁵. These modifications aimed to create a comprehensive and detailed taxonomy, suited for capturing a wide range of cyber incidents.

We used the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset (Delgado et al., 2024) as the basis for the creation of the synthetic dataset. This dataset consists of publicly available cyber incident reports. We reviewed CECILIA-10C-900 and identified at least one cyber incident that would match each class/sub-class pair defined in the modified INCIBE taxonomy.

Each selected cyber incident was then manually enriched with fictitious personal data, either by appending it to the original text, or integrating it into the body of the text. These enriched samples served as "seeds" for the creation of the synthetic dataset. Each class was assigned a number of seed samples proportional to its number of subclasses, with the goal of producing a balanced distribution across subclasses.

The generation of cyber incidents was carried out using the Ollama-Mistral 7B (Touvron et al., 2023) large language model (LLM). based on a prompt template. This prompt includes instructions to mimic the style of the seeds and include fabricated sensitive data.

4.2. DATA PROCESSING

The generated text is pre-processed using the following steps:

- Filter out short paragraphs, i.e., those with less than 5 words.

⁴ <https://www.incibe.es/incibe-cert/incidentes/taxonomia>

⁵ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/reference-incident-classification-taxonomy>

- Remove sentences similar to some predefined template phrases using a sentence transformer.
- Join the remaining sentences into a single paragraph.
- Remove special tokens and other artifacts.

4.3. DATA STORAGE

First, the pre-processed texts are organised by categories and saved as text files in a server directory. As it will be explained below, the dataset is later formatted as comma-separated values, to ease interoperability. Below is a sample of the dataset with PII:

TEXT:

Subject: Urgent - Unauthorized Modification Detected on University Research Networks

Dear Security Team,

In the early hours of March 15th, 2023, our threat hunting team detected indicators of an information compromise activity targeting Mr. Yang Medina, a researcher at Stanford University. The attack campaign intensified throughout the morning, culminating in unauthorized modifications to critical research data stored within the university's networks.

Preliminary analysis suggests that the intrusion occurred around 1:44 AM on March 15th, when an unusual pattern of network traffic was detected originating from an IP address (10.120.222.12). Further investigation revealed that this IP address is registered to a data center located in Dallas, Texas.

The compromised data includes sensitive research materials related to the development of a new solar energy technology. Initial assessments indicate that the attacker modified critical components of the research data, potentially jeopardizing ongoing projects and future research efforts.

Immediate actions include:

1. Isolate affected systems and research data from the broader university network.
2. Initiate forensic analysis to identify the extent and nature of the unauthorized modifications.
3. Notify relevant parties, including Mr. Medina, Stanford University administration, and any external collaborators with access to the compromised data.

CLASS: Compromiso Informacion⁶

SUBCLASS: Acceso No Autorizado⁷

4.4. DATA ACCESS

Access to the data will be public, after publication of the dataset. It will have a digital object identifier (DOI) and rich metadata that will describe the features and usage. To align with the FAIR principle of interoperability, we have formatted the dataset as comma-separated values (CSV), which allows for conversion to other semi-structured formats, such as JSON, and even directly to structured formats. Furthermore, in alignment with the FAIR principle of accessibility, the dataset will be published under a Creative Commons licence CC BY-NC 4.0, which “allows reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, for non-commercial purposes only” according to the summary of the licence provided by Creative Commons website. This type of licence is aligned with the conditions of usage of the original data used as seeds for the creation of our synthetic dataset. However, it requires the reusers of the work to provide attribution to the original creators. Creative Commons licences are machine-readable, and they can also be described using RDF⁸. Additionally, the dataset will be accessible through standard internet protocols. Since the annotations regarding the sensitive data to be anonymised on the reports are not yet available, the first version of the dataset will be published without them. The published dataset will be updated once we have these annotations.

4.5. DATA EXPLOITATION

The data will be used for future experiments on the wide range of text anonymisation methods and tools, such as the ones proposed in Section 5. Specifically, the experiments will evaluate the assessed models in terms of privacy preservation and the utility of the resulting anonymised text. Furthermore, since the dataset is made publicly available with a CC BY-NC 4.0 licence, any interested third-party can use it for experiments. The rich documentation, especially on the metadata, aligns with the FAIR principle of **reusability**.

4.6. DATA SHARING AND DISSEMINATION

For the purposes of reusability, the dataset will be made publicly accessible on at least one of the following platforms:

- Open Science Framework (OSF) (<https://osf.io/>)
- EUDAT (<https://eudat.eu/>)

⁶ Compromised information

⁷ Unauthorised access

⁸ <https://creativecommons.org/ns>

- Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>)
- OpenCAYLE (<https://open.scayle.es/es/>)
- University of Leon internal data repository (<https://buleria.unileon.es/>)
- SIESTA GitHub (<https://github.com/SIESTA-eu>)

The above repositories are suitable to make the dataset easily **findable**, thereby meeting the first component of the FAIR principle.

4.7. DATA DISPOSAL

The final dataset is to be archived in the identified repositories in Section 4.6 and planned for long-term availability. In addition, since the licence permits sharing and redistribution, third-party users may also archive the dataset in other repositories for reuse.

5. ASSESSMENT OF MODELS FOR TEXT ANONYMISATION

In the context of Task 17.2, we assessed different models for the detection of sensitive data susceptible to be anonymised in unstructured text. In this setting, sensitive data is also referred to as entities. Specifically, we evaluated fourteen state-of-the-art NER-based models using the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset.

5.1. EVALUATION DATASET: CECILIA

The CECILIA-10C-900 dataset (Delgado et al., 2024), created through manual efforts for classifying cyber incidents, has annotated features suitable for text anonymisation. In fact, in contrast to typical text anonymisation datasets, CECILIA comprises an extended number of categories. The raw data for CECILIA has been extracted from six sources based on cyber incidents. These sources include the European Repository of Cyber Incidents⁹, the Council on Foreign Relations¹⁰, the Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (ICANN)¹¹, the Centre for Strategic and International Studies¹², the CISSM Cyber Attacks Database¹³, and the Open Web Application Security Project¹⁴. The final dataset consists of 923 instances with 18 possible entity categories. The categories are presented in Appendix B.

⁹ <https://eurepoc.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.cfr.org/>

¹¹ <https://www.icann.org/>

¹² <https://www.csis.org/>

¹³ <https://cisssm.umd.edu/cyber-events-database>

¹⁴ <https://owasp.org/>

5.2. ASSESSED MODELS

We carry out experiments and evaluation on fourteen state-of-the-art NER-based models across three architectural families:

1. BERT-based models (Devlin et al. 2019):
 - a. dsllim/bert-base-NER: A BERT base model fine-tuned on the CoNLL-2003 NER dataset
 - b. dsllim/bert-large-NER: A larger BERT model fine-tuned for NER tasks.
 - c. dbmdz/bert-base-cased-finetuned-conll03-english: A BERT base cased model fine-tuned on the CoNLL-2003 German dataset
 - d. dbmdz/bert-large-cased-finetuned-conll03-english: A BERT large cased model fine-tuned on the CoNLL-2003 English dataset
 - e. elastic/distilbert-base-uncased-finetuned-conll03-english: A DistilBERT base uncased model fine-tuned on the CoNLL-2003 English dataset for NER
2. XLM-RoBERTa models (Conneau et al., 2020):
 - a. xlm-roberta-large-finetuned-conll03-english: An XLM-RoBERTa large model fine-tuned on the English CoNLL-2003 dataset for NER
 - b. Jean-Baptiste/roberta-large-ner-english: A RoBERTa large model fine-tuned on the CoNLL-2003 English dataset for NER
 - c. Davlan/xlm-roberta-base-ner-hrl: An XLM-RoBERTa base model fine-tuned for high-resource languages NER
 - d. Davlan/xlm-roberta-large-ner-hrl: An XLM-RoBERTa large model fine-tuned for high-resource languages NER
 - e. Davlan/bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl: A multilingual BERT base cased model fine-tuned for high-resource languages NER
3. spaCy models (Honnibal and Montani, 2017):
 - a. spacy/en_core_web_sm: A small-sized model optimised for CPU usage, suitable for basic tasks where resource efficiency is important
 - b. spacy/en_core_web_md: A medium-sized model that strikes a balance between performance and accuracy, also optimised for CPU usage
 - c. spacy/en_core_web_lg: A large model providing higher accuracy, optimised for CPU usage, and suitable for more demanding NLP tasks
 - d. spacy/en_core_web_trf: A transformer-based model offering state-of-the-art performance, optimised for GPU usage, ideal for tasks requiring the highest accuracy

These models were pre-trained on the CoNLL-2003 English dataset (i.e., a traditional NER benchmark) and with selected OntoNotes 5.0 documents (i.e., a dataset widely used as an alternative to CoNLL-2003). Appendix C explains the mapping (i.e., differences and

equivalences) between CECILIA entities to those in OntoNotes and CoNLL-2003. Finally, in Appendix D, we compare CECILIA annotation with standard annotation schemes.

All experiments were conducted under the following experimental settings:

- **Hardware Environment:** All experiments were conducted on a single NVIDIA Titan XP GPU with 12GB VRAM, running CUDA 11.2. The hardware selection ensured sufficient computational resources for evaluating transformer-based models while maintaining a practical setup representative of typical enterprise deployment environments.
- **Software Environment:** A Docker container running on Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS operating system. For each model, we utilized the following software configuration:
 - Python version 3.8.10
 - PyTorch version 1.10.0
 - Transformers version 4.18.0
 - SpaCy version 3.2.0

The code of the experiments is accessible at the SIESTA Github ([link](#)¹⁵).

6. RESULTS OF TEXT ANONYMISATION EXPERIMENTS

Table 2 juxtaposes the results of the experiments with the diverse models, showing their performances.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/WP17/tree/main/Task%2017.2>

Model Category	Models	Fine-tuned	Size	Performance		
				Precision	Recall	F-1
BERT-based Models	dslim/bert-base-NER	Yes	108M	0.91	0.60	0.72
	dslim/bert-large-NER	Yes	334M	0.90	0.62	0.73
	dbmdz/bert-base-cased-finetuned-conll03-english	Yes	110M	0.75	0.67	0.71
	dbmdz/bert-large-cased-finetuned-conll03-english	Yes	340M	0.93	0.70	0.80
	elastic/distilbert-base-uncased-finetuned-conll03-english	Yes	66M	0.91	0.57	0.70
XLM-RoBERTa Models	Davlan/xlm-roberta-base-ner-hrl	Yes	277M	0.93	0.56	0.70
	xlm-roberta-large-finetuned-conll03-english	Yes	550M	0.89	0.64	0.74
	Jean-Baptiste/roberta-large-ner-english	Yes	355M	0.89	0.64	0.74
	Davlan/xlm-roberta-large-ner-hrl	Yes	559M	0.93	0.55	0.69
	Davlan/bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	Yes	177M	0.92	0.58	0.71
spaCy Models	spacy/en_core_web_sm	No	13M	0.81	0.78	0.79
	spacy/en_core_web_md	No	35M	0.81	0.76	0.78
	spacy/en_core_web_lg	No	560M	0.84	0.80	0.82
	spacy/en_core_web_trf	No	400M	0.90	0.87	0.87

Table 2: Performance of assessed models on CECILIA dataset

The analysis of the results revealed several significant patterns:

- Precision-recall trade-offs:** Most models demonstrated a clear trade-off between precision and recall. The BERT-based models generally exhibited higher precision (0.90–0.93) at the expense of lower recall (0.55–0.70), while spaCy models showed more balanced precision-recall ratios.
- Entity type performance:** All models performed well on common entity types (PER/PERSON, ORG, LOC/GPE) but struggled with specialised cybersecurity entities. No model consistently detected URL entities, except dbmdz/bert-large-cased-finetuned-conll03-english.
- Model size impact:** Larger models generally delivered better performance, but with diminishing returns. The spaCy transformer model (en_core_web_trf) achieved the highest overall micro-F1 score (0.87) despite having a smaller parameter count than the largest XLM-RoBERTa model.

- **Training data influence:** Models fine-tuned specifically on NER tasks consistently outperformed general-purpose language models, indicating the importance of specialised training even with smaller model architectures.

7. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

7.1. SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

This work package addressed the challenges of text anonymisation in the context of cybersecurity-related unstructured text, focusing on two core contributions: the creation of a synthetic dataset and the evaluation of state-of-the-art NER-based anonymisation models. The key findings and outcomes are summarised below:

- We created a novel, publicly shareable synthetic dataset simulating cyber incident reports, enriched with fictitious personal data. This dataset was generated using a taxonomy-informed prompt strategy and the Ollama-Mistral 7B large language model.
- Fourteen NER-based models were assessed on their ability to detect sensitive entities. Evaluations considered both precision and recall.
- Transformer-based models (particularly spaCy's `en_core_web_trf` and `dbmdz/bert-large-cased-finetuned-conll03-english`) showed superior F1 score, and precision-recall trade-off, which indicates that these architectures effectively capture the contextual relationships necessary for advanced NER tasks.
- While larger models generally performed better, the computational requirements increased significantly with model size. The Titan XP GPU proved adequate for inference, but showed limitations during training phases for the largest models, e.g., processing approximately 20–30 examples per second for XLM-RoBERTa-large compared to 120–150 for DistilBERT.
- The absence of a high performance for cybersecurity-specific entities (URLs, IPs, email addresses) suggests that current pre-trained models require additional fine-tuning on domain-specific corpora.

7.2. FUTURE WORK AND SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

In the light of the work done in this WP, several concrete improvements and research extensions can be proposed. First, the taxonomy and annotation guidelines should be further refined to take into account the re-identification risk of quasi-identifiers, especially when they appear in combination. This would enhance both model training and evaluation. Expanding the synthetic dataset to include more diverse writing styles, multilingual samples, and complex incident structures would also improve the generalisability of model evaluations. Furthermore, introducing adversarial examples and ambiguous inputs into the evaluation process can help identify model weaknesses under non-standard conditions.

In terms of methodology, the development of context-aware anonymisation techniques that incorporate semantic understanding of the surrounding text to determine how sensitive an entity is, e.g. determining whether a detected entity is a direct or a quasi identifier. Finally, optimisation techniques to reduce inference time for transformer-based models would enhance their practical utility.

7.3. LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES

During the period when the WP17 has taken place, we have had two unplanned issues. First, we had to apply for a change in the orientation of the unstructured text dataset, i.e. from Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM) reports to cyber incident reports. Moreover, the hiring of the postdoc, which was planned for autumn 2024, had to be delayed until April 2025 due to administrative issues. As a result, we have not been able to annotate the synthetic reports yet. We plan to enrich the dataset with annotations at document level, i.e. the topic of the report, and at entity level, i.e. in sensitive entities prone to be anonymised (both direct identifiers or quasi-identifiers), the type of entity. Nonetheless, the current lack of annotations do not interfere with the rest of the Work Packages, either ongoing or future work packages. This task will be resumed in WP19, which explicitly includes among its objectives to refine, continue and synchronise the work carried out within different use cases.

Another limitation is that we have not collected user feedback. The goal of task 19.4 (WP19) is to evaluate the proof of concept (PoC) developed in WP17 for anonymizing data in sensitive text documents, refine it to obtain better anonymisation and subsequent text classification performance, and integrate it into the EOSC ecosystem. During task 19.4, we plan to collect and incorporate feedback from actual users to enhance the usability and relevance of the anonymisation tool within the EOSC platform.

Finally, LLM-based models have not been assessed for text anonymisation. While LLMs have been proven to be effective anonymisers and can significantly impact the growth of text anonymisation, many state-of-the-art LLMs currently offer only Software as a Service (SaaS) and/or Data as a Service (DaaS). This limitation hinders the independent development and deployment of models that would have benefited from LLMs.

REFERENCES

- Alistair E. Johnson, Lucas Bulgarelli, and Tom J. Pollard. 2020. “De-identification of free-text medical records using pre-trained bidirectional transformers”. In Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Health, Inference, and Learning (CHIL '20) ed. New York, United States: n.p. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3368555.3384455>.
- Alexis Conneau, Kartikay Khandelwal, Naman Goyal, Vishrav Chaudhary, Guillaume Wenzek, Francisco Guzmán, Edouard Grave, Myle Ott, Luke Zettlemoyer and Veselin Stoyanov. 2020. “[Unsupervised Cross-lingual Representation Learning at Scale](#)”. In Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, pages 8440–8451, Online. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.747>.
- Anthi Papadopoulou, Pierre Lison, Lilja Øvrelid and Ildikó Pilán. 2022. “Bootstrapping Text anonymisation Models with Distant Supervision”. In Proceedings of the Thirteenth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference: 4477–4487 n.p. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.lrec-1.476/>.
- Benet Manzaneres-Salor and David Sánchez. 2025. “Enhancing text anonymisation via re-identification risk-based explainability.” Knowledge-Based Systems 310 (January): 112945. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2024.112945>.
- Fadi Hassan, David Sánchez and Josep Domingo-Ferrer. 2023. “Utility-Preserving Privacy Protection of Textual Documents via Word Embeddings”. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering 35, no. 1 (January): 1058-1071. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9419784>.
- Hanna Yukhymenko, Robin Staab, Mark Vero and Martin Vechev. 2024. “A Synthetic Dataset for Personal Attribute Inference”. In Proceedings of 38th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2024) Track on Datasets and Benchmarks. <https://openreview.net/forum?id=1nqfIQIBf#discussion>.
- Hugo Touvron, Thibaut Lavril, Gautier Izacard, Xavier Martinet, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Timothée Lacroix, Baptiste Rozière, et al. 2023. “LLaMA: Open and Efficient Foundation Language Models.” arXiv, February 27, 2023. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.13971>.
- Ildikó Pilán, Pierre Lison, Lilja Øvrelid, Anthi Papadopoulou, David Sánchez and Montserrat Batet. 2022. “The Text anonymisation Benchmark (TAB): A Dedicated Corpus and Evaluation Framework for Text anonymisation.” Computational Linguistics 48, no. 4 (December): 1054-1101. https://doi.org/10.1162/coli_a_00458.
- Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee and Kristina Toutanova. 2019. “BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding”. In Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers), pages 4171–4186, Minneapolis, Minnesota. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/N19-1423/>.

- Juan J. Delgado, Eduardo Fidaldo, Enrique Alegre, Andrés Carofilis-Vasco and Alicia Martínez-Mendoza. 2024. “CECILIA: Enhancing CSIRT Effectiveness with Transformer-Based Cyber Incident Classification”. In Proceedings of the First International Conference on Natural Language Processing and Artificial Intelligence for Cyber Security, pages 186–195, Lancaster, UK. International Conference on Natural Language Processing and Artificial Intelligence for Cyber Security. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.nlpaics-1.21/>.
- Matthew Honnibal and Ines Montani, 2017. spaCy 2: Natural language understanding with Bloom embeddings, convolutional neural networks and incremental parsing.
- Olexandr Yermilov, Vipul Raheja and Artem Chernodub. 2023. “Privacy- and Utility-Preserving NLP with Anonymized Data: A case study of Pseudonymization”. In Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Trustworthy Natural Language Processing (TrustNLP 2023), pages 232–241, Toronto, Canada. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2023.trustnlp-1.20/>.
- Pierre Lison, Ildikó Pilán, David Sánchez, Montserrat Batet and Lilja Øvrelid. 2021. “Anonymisation Models for Text Data: State of the Art, Challenges and Future Directions”. In Proceedings of the 59th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and the 11th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (Volume 1: Long Papers) ed. Online: n.p. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.acl-long.323>.
- Rajitha Hathurusinghe, Isar Nejadgholi and Miodrag Bolic. 2021. “A Privacy-Preserving Approach to Extraction of Personal Information through Automatic Annotation and Federated Learning”. In Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Privacy in Natural Language Processing, pages 36–45, Online. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2021.privatenlp-1.5/>.
- Robin Staab, Mark Vero, Mislav Balunović and Martin Vechev. 2025. “Language models are advanced anonymizers”. In Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Conference on Learning Representations. <https://openreview.net/forum?id=82p8VHRsaK>.
- Shreya Singhal, Andres F. Zambrano, Maciej Pankiewicz, Xiner Liu, Chelsea Porter, and Ryan S. Baker. 2024. “De-Identifying Student Personally Identifying Information with GPT-4”. In Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Educational Data Mining, pages: 559-565. <https://educationaldatamining.org/edm2024/proceedings/2024.EDM-short-papers.57/index.html>.
- Tianyu Xiaodan, Xiaodan Zhu and Iryna Gurevych. 2024. “Robust Utility-Preserving Text anonymisation Based on Large Language Models.” arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.11770>.
- Tobias Deußer, Max Hahnbück, Tobias Uelwer, Cong Zhao, Christian Bauckhage and Rafet Sifa. 2025. “Resource-Efficient anonymisation of Textual Data via Knowledge Distillation from Large Language Models”. In Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Computational Linguistics: Industry Track, pages 243–250, Abu Dhabi, UAE. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2025.coling-industry.20/>.

- Tom Brown, Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder, Malanie Subbiah, Jared D. Kaplan, Prafulla Dhariwal, Arvind Neelakantan, et al. 2020. "Language Models are Few-Shot Learners". In Proceedings of 34th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2020), Vancouver, Canada. ed. Vol. 33, pages 1877–1901. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.5555/3495724.3495883>.
- Tzvika Hartman, Michael D. Howell, Jeff Dean, Ronit Slyper, Itay Laish, Oren Gilon, Danny Vainstein, et al. 2020. "Customization scenarios for de-identification of clinical notes". BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making 20, no. 14 (January): 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-020-1026-2>.
- Yangsibo Huang, Zhao Song, Danqi Chen, Kai Li and Sanjeev Arora. 2020. "TextHide: Tackling Data Privacy in Language Understanding Tasks". In Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP ed. <https://aclanthology.org/2020.findings-emnlp.123/>.
- Yangsibo Huang, Zhao Song, kai Li and Sanjeev Arora. 2020. "InstaHide: Instance-hiding Schemes for Private Distributed Learning". In Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR 119:4507-4518 ed. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v119/huang20i.html>.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A - TEXT GENERATION ENGINE

- Primary Model**: Mistral 7B (7 billion parameters)
- Model Size**: ~4.1GB (quantized), ~13.5GB (full precision)
- Architecture**: Transformer-based decoder model
- Serving Infrastructure**: Ollama (local inference server)
- API Interface**: Dual compatibility (OpenAI-compatible `/v1/chat/completions`` and native `/api/generate``)

APPENDIX B - CECILIA ENTITIES

The following provides an overview of the NER categories used in the CECILIA dataset:

- **Person:** This refers to names of people, including fictional characters. It is similar to CoNLL-03's PER and OntoNotes's PERSON. Examples: "John Smith", "Harry Potter".
- **Norp:** It refers to nationalities, religious or political groups. It is identical to OntoNotes NORP category. Examples: "American", "Christian", "Republican".
- **Facilities:** This includes buildings, airports, highways, bridges, critical infrastructure. It is similar to OntoNotes's FAC, but with explicit inclusion of critical infrastructure. Examples: "JFK Airport", "Brooklyn Bridge", "Power Plant".
- **GPE_Location:** This refers to countries, cities, states, municipalities, etc. It combines OntoNotes GPE category. Examples: "United States", "Madrid", "California".
- **Location:** This includes natural formations, such as mountains, rock formations, seas, rivers. It is similar to OntoNotes's LOC, but more focused on natural geographical features. Examples: "Rocky Mountains", "Mediterranean Sea", "Amazon River".
- **Organisation:** This includes organisations, companies or institutions. It is similar to CoNLL-03's ORG and OntoNotes's ORG. Examples: "Microsoft", "United Nations", "Harvard University".
- **Group:** This refers to cybercriminal groups, hacker groups. It is a specialised subcategory not explicitly in OntoNotes. Examples: "Anonymous", "Lazarus Group", "APT29".
- **Date:** This refers to absolute dates, relative dates or time periods. It is identical to OntoNotes's DATE. Examples: "January 1, 2023", "last week", "summer 2020".
- **Time:** This refers to any time period less than a day. It is identical to OntoNotes's TIME. Examples: "3:30 PM", "midnight", "morning".
- **Money:** This refers to monetary values with their units. It is identical to OntoNotes's MONEY. Examples: "500€", "1000\$", "five million dollars".
- **Quantities:** This includes measurements of weight, distance, etc. It is identical to OntoNotes's QUANTITY. Examples: "5 kilometres", "20 pounds", "three terabytes".
- **Numbers_O:** Ordinal numbers such as First, second, third, etc. It is identical to the OntoNotes entity ORDINAL.
- **Numbers_C:** Cardinal numbers and numbers that do not fall into other categories. It is identical to OntoNotes's CARDINAL. Examples: "ten", "42", "several".
- **URL:** This refers to any Uniform Resource Locator, i.e., any web address. It is a peculiar category not in standard OntoNotes or CoNLL. Examples: "https://example.com", "www.google.com".

- **Emails:** Email addresses. It is a unique category not in standard OntoNotes or CoNLL. Examples: "user@example.com", "contact@company.org".
- **Phone:** Phone numbers. It is a unique category not in standard OntoNotes or CoNLL. Examples: "+1-555-123-4567", "555-1234".
- **Address:** These are postal addresses. It is a unique category not in standard OntoNotes or CoNLL. Example: "123 Main St, New York, NY 10001".
- **IP:** These are Internet Protocol addresses. It is a unique category not in standard OntoNotes or CoNLL. Examples: "192.168.1.1", "2001:0db8:5a3:0000:00:8a2e:0370:7334".

APPENDIX C - DIFFERENCES AND EQUIVALENCES AMONG CECILIA, CoNLL-03 AND ONTONOTES

CoNLL-03 NER Tag Categories

CoNLL-03 (Conference on Natural Language Learning 2003) uses a relatively simple set of 4 entity types in its Named Entity Recognition task. It follows the BIO (Beginning, Inside, Outside) tagging scheme.

Entity Types

- **PER (Person):** This refers to names of people, including fictional characters. Examples are: "John Smith", "Barack Obama", "Harry Potter"
- **ORG (Organisation):** This refers to companies, institutions, agencies, political parties, sports teams, etc. Examples are: "Microsoft", "United Nations", "Manchester United"
- **LOC (Location):** This includes geographical locations, such as countries, cities, states, and addresses. Examples are: "New York", "France", "Mount Everest"
- **MISC (Miscellaneous):** These are entities that don't belong to the above categories. These include nationalities, events, products, works of art, etc. Examples are: "American" (nationality), "World Cup" (event), "Mona Lisa" (artwork)

Tag Format

The BIO scheme results in 9 possible tags:

- O: Outside of a named entity (not an entity)
- B-PER: Beginning of a person's name
- I-PER: Inside/continuation of a person's name
- B-ORG: Beginning of an organisation
- I-ORG: Inside/continuation of an organisation
- B-LOC: Beginning of a location
- I-LOC: Inside/continuation of a location
- B-MISC: Beginning of a miscellaneous entity
- I-MISC: Inside/continuation of a miscellaneous entity

Example Annotation

Text: "John Smith works at Microsoft in New York."

Annotation:

- "John" → B-PER
- "Smith" → I-PER
- "works" → O
- "at" → O
- "Microsoft" → B-ORG
- "in" → O
- "New" → B-LOC
- "York" → I-LOC
- "." → O

OntoNotes 5.0 NER Tag Categories

OntoNotes 5.0 utilises a more refined set of 18 entity types. It also follows the BIO tagging scheme, but with more detailed entity categories.

Entity Types

- **PERSON:** This refers to people, including fictional characters. Examples are: "John Smith", "Barack Obama", "Harry Potter"
- **NORP (Nationalities, Religious or Political groups):** This refers to adjectival forms of locations, religions, or political groups. Examples are: "American", "Christian", "Republican"
- **FAC (Facility):** This includes buildings, airports, highways, bridges, etc. Examples are: "Empire State Building", "JFK Airport", "Golden Gate Bridge"
- **ORG (Organisation):** This includes companies, agencies, institutions, political parties, etc. Examples are: "Microsoft", "FBI", "Harvard University", "Republican Party"
- **GPE (Geo-Political Entity):** This includes countries, cities, states when referring to the government/nation. Examples are: "United States", "New York City", "California"
- **LOC (Location):** This includes non-GPE locations, mountain ranges, bodies of water, etc. Examples are: "Pacific Ocean", "Rocky Mountains", "Sahara Desert"
- **PRODUCT:** This includes objects, vehicles, foods, etc. (not services). Examples are: "iPhone", "Boeing 747", "Coca-Cola"
- **EVENT:** This includes named hurricanes, battles, wars, sports events, etc. Examples are: "World War II", "Super Bowl", "Hurricane Katrina"

- **WORK_OF_ART:** This includes Titles of books, songs, paintings, etc. Examples are: "The Great Gatsby", "Mona Lisa", "Bohemian Rhapsody"
- **LAW:** These are Named documents made into laws. Examples are: "Constitution", "Bill of Rights", "Americans with Disabilities Act"
- **LANGUAGE:** This refers to any named language. Examples are: "English", "Spanish", "Mandarin"
- **DATE:** This refers to absolute or relative dates or periods. Examples are: "January 1, 2020", "yesterday", "last summer"
- **TIME:** This includes times smaller than a day. Examples are: "3:30 pm", "midnight", "lunch time"
- **PERCENT:** This refers to proportion or percentage, including '%'. Examples are: "10%", "one-third", "half"
- **MONEY:** This refers to monetary values, including units. Examples are: "\$10", "20 euros", "five dollars"
- **QUANTITY:** These are measurements, as of weight or distance. Examples are: "10 kilometers", "5 pounds", "three cups"
- **ORDINAL:** These ordinal numbers such as "first", "second", etc.
- **CARDINAL:** These include cardinal numerals that do not fall under another type. Examples are: "ten", "100", "many"

Tag Format

OntoNotes also uses the BIO scheme, resulting in 37 possible tags (O + B-/I- for each of the 18 categories):

Example Annotation

Text: "President Joe Biden will visit New York City on Friday to discuss a \$2 billion investment."

Annotation:

- "President" → O
- "Joe" → B-PERSON
- "Biden" → I-PERSON
- "will" → O
- "visit" → O
- "New" → B-GPE
- "York" → I-GPE

- "City" → I-GPE
- "on" → O
- "Friday" → B-DATE
- "to" → O
- "discuss" → O
- "a" → O
- "\$" → B-MONEY
- "2" → I-MONEY
- "billion" → I-MONEY
- "investment" → O
- "." → O

Key Differences Between CoNLL-03 and OntoNotes

1. **Granularity:** CoNLL-03 comprises four entity types, while OntoNotes: 18 entity types
2. **Entity Type Differences:** CoNLL-03 uses a broader "MISC" category for many entities that OntoNotes categorises specifically. OntoNotes separates "LOC" into "GPE" and "LOC" OntoNotes also includes non-named entities like dates, money, quantities, etc.
3. **Scope:** CoNLL-03 focuses primarily on "proper" named entities. On the other hand, OntoNotes includes numerical expressions, time expressions, and other non-named entities
4. **Data Size:** CoNLL-03 is smaller (1,393 news articles) while OntoNotes is much larger (covering multiple genres including news, broadcast, weblogs)
5. **Usage:** CoNLL-03 is often used as a benchmark due to its simplicity and historical importance while OntoNotes is more comprehensive and used for more detailed entity extraction applications

APPENDIX D - COMPARISON OF CECILIA WITH OTHER ANNOTATION SCHEMES

The CECILIA annotation scheme is a cybersecurity-focused extension of the OntoNotes scheme, with these key differences:

- **Added digital identifiers:** URL, Email, Phone, Address, IP categories reflect a focus on digital/network information.
- **Added "Group" category:** Specific focus on cybercriminal/hacker groups shows a cybersecurity orientation.
- **Split of locations:** Distinction between GPE_Location and Location (similar to OntoNotes GPE vs LOC).
- **Missing categories compared to OntoNotes:** PRODUCT, EVENT, WORK_OF_ART, LAW, LANGUAGE (these may be less relevant for cybersecurity analysis).

This annotation scheme is optimised for cybersecurity threat intelligence and digital forensics applications, with particular attention to identifying entities that might be relevant in cyber incident reports, threat intelligence, or network security contexts.

Appendix Table D.1 presents the similarity and differences among the 3 datasets and their tagging schemes.

CECILIA Tags	CoNLL-03	OntoNotes Tags	Description
Person	PER	PERSON	Names of people, including fictional characters
Norp	MISC (partial)	NORP	Nationalities, religious or political groups
Facilities	LOC (Partial)	FAC	Buildings, airports, highways, bridges, critical infrastructure
GPE_Location	LOC (Partial)	GPE	Countries, cities, states
Location	LOC (Partial)	LOC	Natural formations: mountains, seas, rivers
Organisation	ORG	ORG	Organisations, companies, institutions
Group	ORG (Partial)	ORG (Partial)	Cybercriminal groups, hacker groups (unique to CECILIA)
Date	-	DATE	Absolute or relative dates, time periods
Time	-	TIME	Time periods less than a day
Money	-	MONEY	Monetary values with units
Quantities	-	QUANTITY	Measurements of weight, distance, etc.
Numbers_O	-	ORDINAL	First, second, third, etc.
Numbers_C	-	CARDINAL	Numbers not in other categories
URL	-	-	Web addresses (unique to CECILIA)
Email	-	-	Email addresses (unique to CECILIA)
Phone	-	-	Phone numbers (unique to CECILIA)
Address	-	-	Physical addresses (unique to CECILIA)
IP	-	-	IP addresses (unique to CECILIA)
-	MISC	PRODUCT	Products, objects, vehicles (not in CECILIA)
-	MISC (partial)	EVENT	Named hurricanes, battles, wars, sports events (not in CECILIA)
-	MISC (partial)	WORK_OF_ART	Titles of books, songs, paintings (not in CECILIA)
-	-	LAW	Named documents made into laws (not in CECILIA)
-	-	LANGUAGE	Any named language (not in CECILIA)
-	MISC (partial)	PERCENT	Percentage values (not in CECILIA)

Appendix Table D1: Comparison among CECILIA, CoNLL-03 and OntoNotes NER tags